

DISEMBODIED VOICES: A KINECT VIRTUAL CHOIR CONDUCTOR

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ABSTRACT

"Disembodied voices" is an interactive environment designed for an expressive, gesture-based musical performance. The motion sensor Kinect, placed in front of the performer, provides the computer with the 3D space coordinates of the two hands. The application is designed according to the metaphor of the choir director: the performer, through gestures, is able to run a score and to produce a real-time expressive interpretation. The software, developed by the authors, interprets the gestural data and controls articulated events to be sung and expressively performed by a virtual choir. Hence the name of the application: you follow the conductor's gestures, hear the voices but don't see any singer. The system also provides a display of motion data, a visualization of the part of the score performed at that time, and a representation of the musical result processed by the compositional algorithm.

1. INTRODUCTION

Kinect¹ is a motion sensing input device launched by Microsoft in the autumn of 2010. It appears as a horizontal black bar connected to a motorized base and it consists of three devices: a RGB camera, a depth sensor and a multi-array microphone. Based on software developed by Rare² and PrimeSense³, the system can interpret specific gestures using an infrared projector and camera and a special microchip to track the movements of individuals in three dimensions. In conjunction with its native video game console⁴, Kinect allows the user to experiment with a completely hands free interaction using a natural interface based on gestures and spoken commands. Following a world-wide sales record⁵ and under the pressure of a growing interest by researchers and programmers, Microsoft released a non commercial Kinect software development kit (SDK) for Windows 7 on June 2011, which allows developers to write Kinect applications in C++ and other programming languages. So many interesting applications have been developed in the fields of robotics,

¹ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kinect>

² <http://www.rare.net/>

³ <http://www.primesense.com/4>

⁴ the Microsoft Xbox 360

⁵ PCWorld, Matt Peckham, Mar 9, 2011

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Figure 1. Kinect's sensing devices.

contents display and managing, video conferencing, video surveillance, medicine, rehabilitation and surgery. Since this kinetic user interface has the ability to extend the freedom and the expressivity of the user, it has also caught the attention of musicians. Motion data can be transmitted without cables and used to feed microcontrollers like Arduino⁶ or can be addressed to computers for sound production. Most musical applications developed with the Kinect tend to imitate or reproduce traditional instrumental performance practice.

In this paper we introduce "Disembodied voices", a system where a conductor plays a score written for a compositional algorithm. Following the traditional conductor's practice, the right hand is used to indicate the attacks and the left hand to perform expressive interaction. The idea to interact with a computer to obtain musical expressive performances through gestural inputs is not new (among the others we quote the "Digital Baton" by Marrin and Paradiso⁷ and "Personal Orchestra" by Borchers and others⁸). However, "Disembodied voices" is not only a virtual conductor application but it is also an interactive composition system where gesture may contribute to articulate musical features in a pre-established formal framework. The space between Kinect and the conductor is empty and no haptic feedback is provided: so audio and visual feedback are necessary to guide the conductor during the performance.

We will first introduce the historical background which inspired this work. This part will be followed by a description of the system interaction between hands movement and the specific musical contents of the application. Then more details on the effective implementation of the system will follow and a brief discussion on performing with no touch instruments will conclude the presentation.

⁶ <http://www.arduino.cc/>

⁷ Digital Baton, MIT Media Lab 1996

⁸ Personal Orchestra, Media Compting Group 2002

Figure 2. Robert Moog's Etherwave Theremin. (Figure taken from the website fig:theremin)

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 The Theremin and Kinect

The Theremin is "the first truly responsive electronic instrument" [1]. It uses a simple capacitance measurement to sense the proximity of the player's hand. This electric field sensibility provides the first no touch interface to the Theremin, which can also be considered as a kinetic interface instrument. Due to these important features, and although it is the oldest among the electronic instruments, the Theremin is incredibly close to the most recent sensor Kinect. Two are the main common features: the imaginary control surface and the natural user interface which allows manipulation.

2.2 The Theremin's playing technique

In playing the Theremin the musician stands in front of the instrument and moves his hands near two metal antennae: one vertical and one round on the left. The Theremin has two oscillators working on non audible range frequencies. One has a fixed frequency and the other a variable one. The difference between the frequencies of the two oscillators creates difference tones which belong to the audible range. By moving his hands towards the antennae, the performer varies the capacitance between his body and the instrument. This variation is used to shift the frequency of the second oscillator (right antenna) and to control the gain of an amplifier circuit (left antenna). The technique used to play the Theremin is easy to learn but hard to control, since it lacks any visual reference and returns no haptic feedback.

2.3 Clara Rockmore's Method for Theremin

Clara Rockmore, expert violinist, virtuoso of the Theremin and author of a method⁹ written to help people to approach the study of this difficult instrument, imagines the control surface of the Theremin like a violin with one long string [2]. The difficulty lies in the fact that the performer must identify and remember the positions of the individual sounds in space along the imaginary string. To avoid a continuous effect of portamento, the movement from one sound to another must be fast and precise. Moreover, while phrasing is limited when performing with traditional instruments by the bow length for strings or the breathing

duration for voices, the Theremin phrasing is infinite and, contrary to what happens in most of the acoustic instruments, it must be voluntarily and arbitrarily interrupted. This occurs thanks to the interaction between the two hands: at the end point of the phrase the amplitude of the sound is reduced to a minimum, thus interrupting the sound. The same technique is used for the staccato. Such a technique implies sound manipulation that enhances expressivity. The Theremin control space has two dimensions and is completely imaginary. Playing the instrument requires a highly developed kinesthetic sense: it is not only necessary to recognize the position in space (proprioception), but also to have the ability to understand the extent, direction and weight of the movements (kinesthesia). According to Buxton [3] the success of the Theremin would be right in this direct relationship between hands position in the control space and the continuous sound feedback that allows the player to build his own mental map for playing the instrument.

2.4 The sensor chair

Our every day life actions take place in a 3D space where we primarily orient ourselves through the sense of sight. Traditionally, however, control surfaces, of both acoustic and virtual instruments, are two-dimensional. Even if the action necessary to play them belong to the natural 3D space, the control surfaces are and remain two-dimensional. The novelty introduced by a no touch system like "Sensor Chair"¹⁰ is interesting precisely because it introduces for the first time the concept of a three-dimensional control surface. The "Sensor chair" is a device that measures the hands and feet position and motion of a seated occupant. It was developed for MIT Digital Expression Conference in October of 1994 and it has been used as one of the performance instruments in Tod Machover's "Brain Opera"¹¹. A copper plate affixed to the top of the chair cushion is a transmitting antenna being driven at roughly 70 kHz. When a person is seated in the chair, he/she effectively becomes an extension of this antenna; his/her body acts as a conductor which is capacitively coupled with the transmitter plate. Four sensors provide the "xy" plane position for the hand as well as "z" position of the hand's distance from the sensor plane. These coordinate data have been used to launch a sound and adjust its volume (xy) and to change its timbral characteristics (z), or to divide the xy plane into many zones which contained different sounds, etc. Users thus deal with discrete 2D (xy) plus 1D (z) control space.

3. HANDS MOVEMENT TAXONOMY

3.1 The 3D space of "Disembodied voices"

Following Leonardo da Vinci's Vitruvian man representation, the space around the human body is more or less spherical. This is due to the fact that the human body has a center represented by the torso and limbs which constitute, in their full extent, the periphery. Moreover, as the

⁹ Clara Rockmore, Method for Theremin

¹⁰ <http://web.media.mit.edu/~joep/TTT.BO/chair.html>

¹¹ <http://park.org/Events/BrainOpera/>

Figure 3. Left hand space subdivision showing the "a", "b" and "c" zones

man looks at the world from his eyes, the most elementary form of organization of physical space consists of taking one's body as a reference center and to place objects around him by distinguishing three types of simultaneous relations "front-back", "right-left", "over-under". This is the reason why it may be more convenient to represent a point in the 3D space with its spherical coordinates. The processing of Kinect data in "Disembodied voices" is based on such a representation.

3.2 Space subdivision and sound controls

Considering hands position we get the radius (r) for arms extension, the azimuth angle (θ) for the hands direction in the horizontal or transverse plane and zenith or elevation (ϕ) for hands direction in the vertical or sagittal plane. The continuous 3D space is then divided in discrete regions by using threshold values for both radius and azimuth in order to define subspaces with specific signification contents for the performance. The model of subdivision of the space used for data mapping is illustrated in Fig.3. When the hand moves upwards or downwards it causes a variation of the value of the zenith which will affect the dynamics of sound, using the common metaphor of "low-piano" and "high-forte". A demarcation line in front of the performer, which depends on a radius threshold value, will bring to another subspace dedicated to the control of a spectrum frequency shift effect. The frequency shift value is minimal near the threshold and grows gradually pushing the hand forward. In Fig.3, using a point of view placed above the performer's head, you see the hand movement in the transverse plane. By adding another threshold on the azimuth we create another subspace which will be dedicated to the control of a modulation effect. Such as for the previous effect the modulation will reach its minimum in the vicinity of the threshold and will gradually increase as the hand goes further away. These thresholds create three portions of space (letters "a", "b" and "c"). In the "a" zone left hand movements only lead to the dynamics control. In the "b" zone left hand movements activate both modulation effect and dynamics control while in the "c" zone they still affect the volume but the activated effect is the frequency shifter.

action (zone)	gesture	r	θ	ϕ
gain (a)	LH-C	-	-	y
freq.s. 1 (c)	LH-C	>25%	<25%	-
mod. (b)	LH-C	>25%	>25%	-
cues	RH-FT	max	0	<10%
stop	RH-RT	<20%	0	max
freq.s. 2	RH-C	-	x	-

Table 1. Summary of the gestual mode of interaction.

3.3 Data mapping

"Disembodied voices" manages two types of data: continuous controls for expressive interaction and discrete controls for triggering events (cues). The latter are performed by the right hand while reaching the extreme forward/highest zone (minimum zenith) for cues attacks, and the extreme rear/lower zone (minimum radius) for stopping the performance. These movements need to be impulsive. Therefore, for a correct execution, the hand has to reach the position and then immediately withdraw from the affected area. This is crucial for cues management. A too long stay of the right hand in the active zone can lead to the activation of more cues one behind the other, disturbing the behavior of the compositional algorithms. Continuous controls are mainly associated with the movements of the left hand. They are divided into: continuous signals, active all over the field range of mapped data (zenith for the dynamics) and continuous signals active only after passing a threshold (azimuth for modulation and radius for frequency shift). A second frequency shifter has been added in order to create beatings between the transposed sounds. This effect is activated by the right hand while moving into a dedicated subspace defined by another threshold on azimuth. All hand movements and mapping are summarized in Table 1 with the following conventions: gain in zone "a"; frequency shift 1 in zone "c", modulation in zone "b". LH-C, Left Hand Continuous control; RH-C, Right hand Continuous control; RH-FT, Right Hand Front Trigger control; RH-RT, Right Hand Rear Trigger control.

4. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Before describing technical details on the system implementation we will focus our attention on the compositional algorithm which represents the system's core. Then the remaining functional blocks of the application will be briefly described. The first block is the application Synapse¹² which detects data from Kinect. The second and third blocks are programmed by the authors with Max/MSP¹³ and are divided into two distinct patches, one for gestural data processing and the other one for sound processing. The communication between Synapse and Max as well as between the two Max patches is done via OSC¹⁴ as illustrated on the flowchart on fig.4.

¹² <http://synapsekinect.tumblr.com/>

¹³ <http://cycling74.com/>

¹⁴ <http://opensoundcontrol.org/introduction-osc>

Figure 4. Overall flowchart of "Disembodied voices".

4.1 The compositional algorithm

The compositional algorithm are inspired by the model of Ligeti's micropolyphony¹⁵ which is usually generated by a canonic compositional technique [4]. However, we considered the micropolyphony as a chaotic mass movement of a given number of voices from one or more pitches towards one or many target pitches, as can be seen in Fig.5. The movement is divided into three stages and can be represented by a breakpoint function which requires at least three couples of data: start pitch/first stage duration, target pitch/transition stage duration, target pitch/last stage duration. The start pitch and the target pitch may be the same for all the voices. If they differ, this means that the tract of each voice will be different, generating thus an interesting polyphonic texture. In addition, the starting point of the function can be slightly delayed by a duration value different from voice to voice. This difference produces a kind of automatic canon whose density can be controlled using appropriate delay values. In Max/MSP polyphony management may be realized by using the "poly~" object which easily duplicates voices instances and facilitates their control. Each "poly~" instance performs only one note. The "poly~" objects are grouped in four symbolic sections named, according to the traditional choir voice division, sopranos, altos, tenors and basses, and are consequently labelled. Each cue message contains a label which addresses one of the four vocal sections. The sequence of messages is fixed in advance and depends on the fea-

tures contained in the musical score. After receiving the message, the composition algorithm produces a package of data which is sent to a sampler. We used a patch based on the "sampler~" external¹⁶ to load and manage commercial samples for the voice's synthesis. This is a temporary solution which could next be replaced by a more complex synthesis engine. To obviate the simplicity of the synthesis model and to add expressivity to the performance, sample voices are processed by two effects.

4.2 Digital sound processing

A ring modulator and two frequency shifters are used to translate the spectrum of the sampler's outgoing voices in order to create some non linear spectral distortion. The ring modulator frequency, when active, grows progressively from 0 to 80 Hz. The frequency shift is obtained by real time analysis and resynthesis of the sound through FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) and IFFT (Inverse Fast Fourier Transform) and it is used in a range comprised between 0 to 600 Hz. These effects are introduced when willing to create tension during the performance as they distort the original voices and lead to a more aggressive sound. The effects amount is controlled by continuous gestural data as described afterwards. The possibility of intervening with two parallel frequency shifters allows overlapping of spectral harmonics thus creating beats for small frequency differences.

¹⁵ <http://qutmusic.pbworks.com/w/page/4663881/micropolyphony>

¹⁶ <http://serge.lemouton.free.fr/maxobjects>

Figure 5. Visualization of the breakpoint function of four delayed voices.

4.3 Gesture acquisition through Synapse

As the Kinect software development kit is only available for the Windows platform we decided to use the Mac and Windows application Synapse which has been created using OpenFrameworks¹⁷ and ofxOpenNI¹⁸. Synapse collects the skeleton bone joints data of the performer and sends them to other applications through the OSC protocol. Synapse sends OSC messages using two different ports, for example ports 12345 and 12347, and receives messages on another port, for example 12346. The traceable joints are: hand, elbow, foot, knee (for all these joints, both right and left), head and torso. To obtain motion data related to a given joint it is necessary to regularly send a message to Synapse with the name of the joint. This prevents Synapse from sending data for all the joints at each frame, which could cause a data loss.

4.4 Conversion and calibration of motion data

As illustrated in Fig.4 the motion data coming from Synapse are sorted into two data flows corresponding to the right and to the left hand, and then converted from three-dimensional to spherical coordinates. These data require further calibration to measure the maximum and minimum extension of the hands of any user. This is automatically processed on the fly, allowing the user to speed up the calibration operation. After taking the "Psi pose"¹⁹ it is enough to hold up your arms forward, upward and sideways. The system will record the maximum and minimum extension of your arms and use them to rescale the data movement. If the user changes it is possible to reset the calibration system pressing the "r" key on the computer keyboard.

4.5 Data mapping

Since the gain is a value that interacts directly with the audio coming from the mixer, its output is continuous and corresponds to a value ranging from -40 dB to 0 dB. The

other audio parameters are mapped on the continuous gestural data by using a "one-to-one" relationship with an exponential transfer function. The expressive interaction of ring modulation and frequency shift are active only after exceeding the threshold corresponding to the 25 percent of the mapped value. The limits are 0-80 Hz for the modulation frequency, and 0-600 Hz for the frequency shift. A stop message is sent when the right hand position passes under 20 percent of the radius value. When the right hand passes under the 10 percent of the zenith value a trigger message is sent to a counter which outputs a specific cue number. All the messages are sent to the second patch via OSC.

5. PERFORMING ON A NO TOUCH INSTRUMENT

An important feedback when playing a musical instrument is the haptic sensation related to the mechanics of the instrument. This feeling is divided into: tactile (pressure, surface curvature, orientation, moisture, friction, etc.) and proprioceptive and kinesthetic sensations [5]. They are so important to be considered as part of the instrumental performance. For example, they allow the players to orient themselves in taking positions, to improve tuning based on simple auditory feedback, to facilitate articulation, phrasing and thus expressiveness, to improve music pieces memorization (via the retention of certain situations resulting from haptic gestural sequences), to perform complex compositions or to read them at sight focusing the eye on the score rather than on the instrument, etc. The characteristic of the no touch instrument is to communicate with the computer through gestures without being in direct contact with the control surface. As a consequence, the haptic feedback in these performances is totally lacking. Rován and Hayward (op. cit.) accurately describe the performance process under these conditions, through the following steps:

1. the performer, who is more or less forced by the system, must have in his/her mind an executive idea (intention)
2. then he/she must run the gesture to perform the intention. Through the control surface (which is imaginary and of different sizes and shapes) the gestural data become sound
3. evaluate his/her action through the vision and the kinesthetic sense
4. hear the resulting sound
5. amend his/her acts through the vision and proprioception
6. change his/her intention by appreciating the resulting sounds
7. and so on

It's obvious that in this scenario the lack of haptic feedback increases the importance of other channels, visual and proprioceptive. The first Max/MSP patch is not only used for gestural data processing but also for producing a visual feedback of the interaction. For that purpose various GUI objects of different sizes and colors have been used to display the current state of the interaction in order to be clear

¹⁷ <http://synapsekinect.tumblr.com/>

¹⁸ <http://kinect.dashhacks.com/ofxopenni>

¹⁹ The so called "Psi pose" is a particular position, similar to the greek letter ψ which allows Kinect to interpret the user's dimensions.

Figure 6. Screenshot of the musical result provided by the compositional algorithm. In particular, starting from the left, a pedal of A (440 Hz), four short A at different octaves, a slide towards a very low A etc.

even far away from the screen. The second patch produces a visual feedback of the result of the compositional algorithm by using a "lcd" object where small spheres display the sounds produced by this algorithm (see Fig.6). Time and pitch values are respectively represented on the "x" and "y" axes. The problem of all these visual feedbacks is that they are produced retrospectively, just after the action has been concluded or the position has been reached. They have only a confirmatory value of the intention once it has been properly completed. Unfortunately they do not have any predictive value with respect to a probable error, and this can be a problem for an application without haptic feedback such as "Disembodied voices". It's known that haptic feedback is useful for the prevention of performance mistakes, as described by O'Modhrain in her PhD dissertation [6]. In the case of "Disembodied voices" a real time 3D display of an avatar of the interpreter could be useful, as well as the design of spherical markers of the 3D control space. The second patch also displays instructions for the performance of each cue. These notes act as a reminder for the conductor and include current event description as well as hints about the expressive interaction to be performed.

6. CONCLUSIONS

"Disembodied voices"²⁰ has many things in common with the Theremin. But, while the Theremin has the same function of a traditional acoustic instrument, designed to play notes and rhythms, "Disembodied voices" is a system which performs a compositional algorithm. This means that some hidden structures are interposed between the gesture and the auditory result without any evidence for the observer. In fact, while the expressive interaction shows a great congruence between visible gesture and sound result, the same cannot be said for cues which are actually simple impulses. There is a non-evident relationship between such impulses and the structural contents of the musical events they pro-

duce. The only clear relationship remains time synchronization between impulses and the events triggering. As the compositional algorithm can be represented by a breakpoints function, a hypothesis of connection between gesture and composition could be to gesturally perform the profile of the function. The system could store the function and use it with predetermined timing characteristics. This could also be a way to build a perceptual link between a natural gesture interaction and a complex act like composing. Another direction of further research concerns the kind of gestural interaction employed in "Disembodied voices". Being strictly bound to the model of the choir conductor, tracked gestures have been limited to those of the hands, while the Kinect device offers much more valid joints like torso, head and so on. Some usability tests need to be performed to verify how non-musician deal with expressive gesture and interact with the application zones boundaries. In the same way the system has to be tested when handling different versions of the compositional algorithm. This could be done by increasing, for example, the number of musical parameters to be controlled and thus dividing the space in more performing zones, by introducing more complex mapping between gesture and sound parameters, or by modifying the rules which articulate the musical parameters flow. These tests should bring interesting points on robustness, limitations or advantages of the different elements which contribute to the overall system. Our hope is to continue this research which can open interesting perspectives for electronic music performance combined with algorithmic composition.

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²⁰ <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oyf7GrMMrL8list=UU1E9xCq8TWqlzessRIzUGxwindex=1feature=plcp>